

Reactions of Nickel (II) Salts with Benzaldimines

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In continuation of our research work on transition and non-transition metal complexes of Schiff bases¹⁻¹⁰, we have undertaken an investigation on the reaction of benzaldimine type of ligands with some metal salts. Two recent publications¹¹ on the proton magnetic resonance studies of paramagnetic nickel(II) complexes containing benzaldimine groups prompted us to report our preliminary results on the reactions of nickel (II) salts with the Schiff bases derived from benzaldehyde and ethylenediamine (= B₂E), and 1,3-diaminopropane-2-ol (= B₂DAP). It also describes the reaction of nickel(II) salts with 4-methylbenzaldehyde and 1,3-diaminopropane-2-ol [= (4-Me-B)₂DAP].

EXPERIMENTAL

All the complexes were prepared by the same general method. An absolute alcohol solution containing 10 mmol. of the diamine and 25 mol. of the benzaldehyde (or, benzaldehyde derivatives) was boiled (under nitrogen atmosphere) for 20 mins. This solution was added to a boiling solution of 10 mmol. of the anhydrous nickel (II) salts (chloride, bromide, or iodide) in 50-60 ml. of absolute alcohol. After boiling for 20 mins, the solution was filtered, which on concentration in a vacuum desiccator yielded crystalline compounds. In some cases addition of cyclohexane promoted the crystallization. The compounds were filtered rapidly under an atmosphere of nitrogen and dried in a vacuum desiccator.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The compounds isolated are moisture sensitive. The elemental analyses (Table 1) correspond to the formula NiLX₂ (where L = a molecule of the ligand and X = Cl, Br, or I) for the complexes, and are paramagnetic with effective magnetic moments ranging from 3.40-3.55 B.M. at room temperature (Table 1). They are soluble in polar organic solvents and are practically non-conducting in 1,2-dichloroethane (molar conductivity found

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TABLE 1

Elemental analyses and room-temperature magnetic moments of nickel(II) Complexes

Compound	Found %		Calc. %		μ_{eff} (B.M.)
	Ni	N	Ni	N	
Ni(B ₂ E)Cl ₂	16.01	7.28	15.93	7.67	3.55
Ni(B ₂ E)Br ₂	12.27	6.00	12.80	6.16	3.48
Ni(B ₂ DAP)Br ₂	11.88	5.52	12.01	5.78	3.40
Ni[(4-Me-B) ₂ DAP]Br ₂	11.00	5.10	11.36	5.47	3.45

for 10^{-3} M solutions of these complexes are between 1.8 and 0.5 ohm⁻¹ cm² mole⁻¹). The electronic spectra (Table 2) of some of these compounds in 1,2-dichloroethane have been measured in the range 76,923–26,000 cm⁻¹ and five absorption bands at $\sim 7,800$ cm⁻¹, $\sim 10,100$ cm⁻¹, $\sim 11,720$ cm⁻¹, $\sim 17,580$ cm⁻¹ and $\sim 19,120$ cm⁻¹ have been recorded.

Attempts to prepare other derivatives, apart from Ni (4-Me-B)₂ DAP Br₂ were unsuccessful.

The molar conductivity results indicate that the complexes are undissociated in 1,2-dichloroethane. The electronic spectra (Table 2) in the same solvent show high extinction

TABLE 2

Electronic spectral data of nickel (II) complexes in 1,2-dichloroethane

Compound	Absorption max., cm ⁻¹ (ϵ molar). Sh = shoulder				
Ni(B ₂ E)Cl ₂	10,100(84)	11,762(50)	17,572(Sh)	19,120(Sh)	
Ni(B ₂ E)Br ₂	7,813(14)	11,202(98)	11,720(80)	17,580(Sh)	19,000(Sh)
Ni(B ₂ DAP)Br ₂	7,890(16)	10,350(100)	11,599(88)	18,800(150)	
Ni[(4-Me-B) ₂ DAP]Br ₂	7,860(20)	10,200(60)	11,670(70)	17,600(Sh)	19,500(Sh)

co-efficients, indicating that the predominant species present in 1,2-dichloroethane in each case is pseudotetrahedral^{12,13}. This is also substantiated by the appearance of a band in the region 7800–7890 cm⁻¹ (Table 2), which may be considered as the diagnostic band for a tetrahedral (or pseudotetrahedral) nickel(II) complex¹⁴.

The room-temperature magnetic moments (Table 1) of the present complexes are well within the range of tetrahedral nickel(II) complexes^{12,14}, although a polymeric octahedral stereochemistry in the solid state cannot, however, be ruled out on the basis of these room-temperature magnetic moments alone. The study of the temperature dependence of the magnetic moments of the present system of complexes can provide more meaningful results,

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on the basis of which definite conclusion could be drawn regarding the stereochemistry of the complexes. However, we could not study the magnetic susceptibilities at various temperatures at the present moment.

The donor and steric properties of the group $-\text{CH}_2\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ (occurs in $\text{N}_1, \text{N}, \text{N}', \text{N}'$ -tetramethyl-1,2-diaminoethane) and $-\text{CH}_2-\text{N}=\text{CH}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{X}$ (occurs in the present ligand systems) appear to be very similar, and it is these types of substituents which can give rise to pseudotetrahedral complexes among the substituted ethylenediamines^{11,15-17}.

Further work on the reaction of this type of ligands with various other metal salts and also on the present complexes is in progress and will be communicated in due course.

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